

Life Skills for Leadership Training Among Students.

Dr. Bipasha Sinha

Associate Professor, Dept. Of Education, S. S. Jalan Girls' College,
University of Calcutta.

Corresponding author- **Dr. Bipasha Sinha**

Email: bipashasinha@gmail.com

Abstract: Leadership is considered one of the important life skills and is trainable like any other skill. Leadership is the process through which one member of a group influences other group members towards attainment of shared group goals. Youth should learn leadership in their development, working well with people by developing them, motivating and empowering the group members. Leadership skills are a set of human skills acquired via learning or direct experiences that are used to handle problems and questions commonly faced in day to day personal and professional life. This paper discusses the concept, importance and strategies of developing leadership training as a life skill among students.

Key Words: Life skill, Leadership training, Student community.

Introduction

Leadership is considered one of the important life skills and is trainable like any other skill. Leadership is the process through which one member of a group influences other group members towards attainment of shared group goals. Youth should learn leadership in their development, working well with people by developing them, motivating and empowering the group members. Some of the leadership skills students can learn include: self confidence, communicating effectively including learning to listen, giving and receiving feedback, working well with people by involving them in meaningful ways; motivating and empowering others and sharing leadership which includes the ability to plan, organize, delegate and assess, accepting differences in people and in their opinions, managing conflict and flexibility etc.

The University Grants Commission (UGC) defines life skills as behaviours used appropriately and responsibly in the management of personal and professional affairs. Leadership skills are a set of human skills acquired via learning or direct experiences that are used to handle problems and questions commonly faced in day to day personal and professional life. Skills stated by the UGC include communication skills, interpersonal skills, time management, teamwork, flexibility, problem solving, professional skills, decision making, leadership abilities and general values. Leadership abilities include leadership skills, managerial skills, entrepreneurial skills, innovative strategies and thinking skills, ethics and solidarity. Leadership skills will help students to examine different types of leadership ideals and judge their own leadership style based on them and on their own strengths and abilities. Training helps students develop multiple skills like time management, self-control, conflict management, team leadership, etc.

The concept of leadership training

Leadership training refers to mastering leadership qualities by demonstrating what a leader's behaviour might look like, modelling that behaviour and practicing it. The greatest lesson in leadership is how competent he is in a crisis situation. Leadership training is an overall effort to develop in a person those qualities that will help him become effective as a leader. When there are competitions, seminars or workshops in educational institutions, then students are allotted certain duties, which help the development of leadership skills.

Leadership Skills

There are basic ten skills identified as essential leadership skills. Firstly, a leader should have the ability to think about or plan the future with imagination or wisdom. He should have fluency, flexibility, originality and clear and detailed thinking for achieving the stipulated goals. Secondly, a leader should be courageous and motivated. Courage means the mental or moral strength to undertake, keep trying, and withstand danger, fear, or difficulty. A skilled leader has a high desire for success and therefore the courage to take risks. Self-motivated leaders motivate others to adopt their style of leadership for attaining goals more consistently. Thirdly, a leader should have internal integrity and sense of responsibility. Internal integrity and sense of responsibility is a state of mind that maintains a harmonious balance between a person's thoughts, emotions, intelligence, etc. As a result there is a kind of consistency in his behaviour which helps him to maintain a strong and steady unity in work, in decision-making, in expressing positive attitude towards others. Fourthly a leader should be humane, compassionate, sympathetic, or generous behaviour or disposition. Fifthly, a leader should be able to do strategic planning. Strategic planning is a process in which an organization's leaders define their vision for the future and identify their organization's goals and objectives. The process includes establishing the

sequence in which those goals should be realized so that the organization can reach its stated vision.

Sixthly, a leader should be focussed. A primary task of leadership is to direct attention. To do so, leaders must learn to focus their own attention. When we speak about being focused, we commonly mean thinking about one thing while filtering out distractions. The leader's focus is transmitted to the followers. Seventhly, a leader should effectively communicate, cooperate and delegate task to his team members, the ability to send and receive correct messages using various media such as oral speech, written speech, gestures, charts, diagrams, etc. Verbal communication like use of orders, suggestions, discussions, etc., keeps the communication process going in workplaces. The leader and the employees work closely together. The success of any team work depends on the ability of the leader to distribute or delegate responsibilities among members which leads to effective completion of task. Eighthly, a leader should have a positive attitude. This means being optimistic about situations and outcomes. People with positive attitudes remain hopeful and see the best even in difficult situations. A leader should not be pessimistic but optimistic. Ninthly, a leader should be trustworthy. Gaining the trust and credibility is important for becoming a leader. If the leader is restless, incompetent in decision-making, confused in solving problems, then he has no acceptance. Frequent changes of decisions, different behaviour at different times in the same situation, are opposite qualities of leader's credibility. Hence in leadership training, leaders are trained to establish himself as a trusted team confidant. Finally, a leader should be able to take feedback from his team after the completion of the task. Feedback is information about how one is doing in effort to reach a goal. Feedback improves learner confidence, motivation to learn and ultimately attain goals. Using positive feedback helps individuals recognize and sharpen their skills, develop their areas of improvement and create a general sense of positivity in the workplace.

Importance of Developing Leadership Skills among Students

In the present day, the job market demands the individuals to possess leadership skills to acquire employment opportunities in positions of technology executive, communication specialist and leadership training and development specialist. For this purpose, it is necessary to train students in leadership skills as it will help them to achieve the desired academic goals, but enhance their professional skills and sustain their living in an appropriate manner. Firstly, to achieve academic goals it is necessary for students to develop leadership skills. These skills will enable them to

make appropriate decisions, implement their tasks genuinely and meticulously and form good relationships with other members in the educational institutions. Secondly, students should have inner desire for self-development. Self-development refers to effective communication skills, inculcating the traits of morality and ethics, generating awareness regarding various aspects, forming constructive viewpoints, enhancing one's personality traits, implementing honesty and truthfulness, recognising ones responsibilities, forming effective terms and relationships with others, making wise decisions and enriching one's overall quality of lives. Putting these traits into practice will lead to effective self-development in a student. Thirdly it is essential for students to be creative. Particularly, when they are working on assignments, reports or projects, then creativity is usually depicted in stating ideas and in the overall presentation. When the students are creative, they can increase their leadership skills by giving ideas and suggestions. Fourthly, Teachers generally encourage team work. The team members are different from each other in terms of natures, skills, capabilities and behavioural traits. In some cases, they carry out their job duties with wholeheartedly whereas, in other cases, they procrastinate. Student leaders are required to inspire and stimulate the mind-sets of other team members towards completion of tasks and functions. Fifthly the student leader should have the Ability to Predict and Make Decisions. Predicting is referred to forecasting, envisaging and calculating. When the leaders are able to predict the future or the behavioural traits of other individuals, they are able to determine the procedures, which would be most effectual in the implementation of tasks. Making decisions is an integral part of the functioning of classroom activities and educational institutions. The student leaders are vested with the authority to make decisions. It is also important for leaders to allow team members to participate in the decision making processes. Decisions made, should be beneficial to all members.

Sixthly, students face certain problems like preparation of assignments, or projects or in acquiring a proper understanding of the academic concepts. Here students need to remain calm, conduct an analysis of the alternatives available and put into practice the alternative that would be most suitable. Student leaders should possess abilities to cope with challenges and guide the other team members too. Seventhly, the implementation of tasks and activities need to be in accordance to the situations. For instance, in educational institutions, when seminars and workshops are organized the teachers give/allot duties to the students. The students are required to implement tasks in accordance to the situations. Students implementing

tasks for the first time should seek assistance and support from teachers or fellow students are not confident. Eighthly, development of professionalism among student leaders are vital if they enable them to achieve personal and professional goals. Professional traits like communicating with other individuals with respect and courtesy, implementing honesty and truthfulness, inculcating the traits of morality and ethics, realizing one's responsibilities, possessing adequate knowledge and information in terms of various tasks, inculcating the traits of diligence, resourcefulness and conscientiousness, adopting the feeling of patriotism, curbing negative viewpoints, forming constructive viewpoints and perspectives regarding the educational institutions etc, ensure that learning methods are put into practice in an appropriate manner. Ninthly, the development of knowledge and skills are regarded as essential, particularly in the case of lesson plans and academic concepts. In order to achieve academic goals, students should have knowledge in preparation of one's assignments, projects, tests and competitions as an integral part of learning. It is also important to encourage students to participate in extra-curricular and creative activities. These include, sports, physical activities, music, singing, dancing, artworks, handicrafts, role playing and so forth. Participation in extra-curricular and creative activities stimulates their mind towards learning. Finally, in some cases, student leaders participate in making provision of literacy skills among students, belonging to deprived and socio-economically backward sections of the society. Whereas, in other cases, students are given the responsibility of collecting various things, such as, food items, clothing, medicines, and other items for the victims of natural calamities and disasters. Thus, the adoption of social responsibility enables the students to effectively contribute towards community well-being.

Strategies for Developing Leadership Skills

As mentioned earlier, Leadership is considered one of the important life skills and is trainable like any other skill. There are various ways to inculcate or train in leadership skills among students. Firstly, student leaders should be taught effective communication skills like speaking, listening and responding. When one is speaking, it is vital for them to communicate factual information and make use of decent language. One should possess effective listening skills and pay attention to the speakers. Also, it is vital for the listeners to respond and give proper feedback. While practicing leadership skills, student leaders should direct, guide and lead individuals in the right direction to achieve goals by using effective communication skills. Secondly, student leaders should be trained to be enthusiastic about the task they are assigned. When

student leaders show enthusiasm and interest, the team members feel comfortable in approaching them with their problems and concerns. It is vital for the leaders to make provision of equal opportunities and not discriminate against others on the basis of caste, creed, race, religion, ethnicity, gender, age, and socio-economic background. Within the classroom settings, there are differences among students but the leader should treat all fellow students with respect and courtesy. Thirdly, student leaders should be trained to be focused towards attaining goals. Student leaders should be disciplined by meeting deadlines in completion of a task and avoiding procrastination. Student leadership needs to focus upon their personal and professional goals. For instance, when one student is helping another in acquiring a better understanding of the lesson plans, he has the major objective of ensuring that his fellow student is able to adequately understand the concepts. In absence of teachers, student leaders need to ensure that discipline is maintained, students are concentrating on their studies and the environmental conditions within the classroom is under control. Fourthly, student leaders should be taught to be familiar with other students within the classroom setting. They need to note their qualities and characteristics. This will help the student leaders to effectively monitor and lead other students and they can perform their job satisfactorily. Student leader should understand the fact that a good leader happens only when there is good team participation. Student leader should keep his team's best interest in mind rather than his own interest. Student leader should be a people's person. Student leader should be approachable, open-minded and friendly. Then only other students will listen to him and follow his instructions. Fifthly, it is vital for the leaders to make use of one's knowledge and understanding and carry out their responsibilities in a well-organized manner. Student leaders should be trained to enable each group member to identify their duties and responsibilities, particularly in the achievement of their academic goals. Sixthly, the student leader should be taught to establish appropriate relation with the teachers, take initiative, offer help and information, obtain guidance and assistance, when needed etc. When the students due to some valid causes are unable to accept responsibilities, they need to communicate valid reasons in a polite and decent manner. But when they feel that accepting responsibilities would prove to be beneficial to them, they should give foremost priority to their work and accept responsibilities. Student leaders should engage in volunteering activities like student-run fundraisers or annual events of their institution. This will help students develop their leadership skills. Seventhly, student leaders should be trained to inspire and motivate others if a team member

needs reassurance or assistance. It is an integral duty of student leaders to adequately counsel and guide the other individuals in providing solutions to their problems by providing satisfactory ideas and suggestions that would be suitable to them. Student leaders need to counsel and guide, particularly in case of students, who experience setbacks in their academic performance or the ones, who experience any personal problems. Eighthly, student leaders should be trained to develop situational awareness and pro-activeness because that will help students see the bigger picture. They should foresee any problems before they occur and allow them time to make alternative plans. Here the student leaders are required to follow a step-by-step approach. These are, stating the problem as simply and clearly as possible, gathering all the relevant information and pertinent resources, brainstorming as many ideas and solutions as one can think of, when there are number of alternatives available, the individuals need to conduct an analysis of all the alternatives and make selection of the most suitable ones, plans need to be designed for utilizing ideas and solutions and following up on the plan is to determine whether the methods used have been suitable or not. Ninthly, student leaders should be trained to keep trying to learn new things as it better their skills and enriches their mind. In order to enhance the system of education, it is necessary to include modern and innovative methods and strategies. It is necessary for student leaders to identify the areas need improvement. After identifying the areas for improvement, it is necessary for the student leaders to put them into practice to enrich the system of education and facilitate the achievement of academic goals. Finally, during the course of implementation of one's goals, student leaders may feel stressed or anxious or frustrated especially when one is overwhelmed by number of responsibilities. Even when leaders have responsibilities, they need to have the appropriate skills and abilities to overcome these negative feelings. The student leaders need to be trained to develop good terms and relationships with all fellow students by behaving in a polite manner with others and put into practice the traits of morality and ethics.

1. Aparna.N and Raakhee A.S (2011). Life Skill Education for Adolescents: its Relevance and Importance. *GESJ: Education Science and Psychology*, 2 (9), 3-7.
2. Bharath, S., Kumar, K.V. (2008). Health Promotion using Life Skills Education Approach for Adolescents in Schools □ Development of a Model. *Journal of Indian Association of Child & Adolescent Mental Health*, 4(1),5□11.
3. CBSE. Life Skills Education and CCE Hand Book. New Delhi. Retrieved from
4. www.cbse.nic.in/cce/life_skills_cce.pdf Hamburg, B.A. (1990). Life-skill Training Preventive Interventions for Young Adolescents. Washington, D.C.: Camegie Council on Adolescent Development.
5. Vranda, M.N. and Chandrassekar, R. M. (2011). Life Skills Education for Young Adolescents □ Indian Experience. *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology*, 37, 9-15.
6. World Health Organization. (1996). Life Skills Education: Planning for Research. Geneva: WHO.72p.
7. http://mhrd.gov.in/adolescence_programme
8. <http://unicef.in/PressReleases/333/Adolescence-Education-Programme>
9. www.unicef.org/lebanon/programs_8008.htm
10. Aparna.N and Raakhee A.S (2011). Life Skill Education for Adolescents: its
11. Relevance and Importance. *GESJ: Education Science and Psychology*, 2 (9), 3-7.
12. Bharath, S., Kumar, K.V. (2008). Health Promotion using Life Skills Education
13. Approach for Adolescents in Schools □ Development of a Model. *Journal of Indian*
14. Association of Child & Adolescent Mental Health, 4(1),5□11.
15. CBSE. Life Skills Education and CCE Hand Book. New Delhi. Retrieved from
16. www.cbse.nic.in/cce/life_skills_cce.pdf
17. Hamburg, B.A. (1990). Life-skill Training Preventive Interventions for Young
18. Adolescents. Washington, D.C.: Camegie Council on Adolescent Development.
19. Vranda, M.N. and Chandrassekar, R. M. (2011). Life Skills Education for Young
20. Adolescents □ Indian Experience. *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied*
21. *Psychology*, 37, 9-15.
22. World Health Organization. (1996). Life Skills Education: Planning for Research.
23. Geneva: WHO.72p.
24. http://mhrd.gov.in/adolescence_programme
25. <http://unicef.in/PressReleases/333/Adolescence-Education-Programme>
26. www.unicef.org/lebanon/programs_8008.htm
27. Aparna.N and Raakhee A.S (2011). Life Skill Education for Adolescents: its
28. Relevance and Importance. *GESJ: Education Science and Psychology*, 2 (9), 3-7.
29. Bharath, S., Kumar, K.V. (2008). Health Promotion using Life Skills Education
30. Approach for Adolescents in Schools □ Development of a Model. *Journal of Indian*
31. Association of Child & Adolescent Mental Health, 4(1),5□11.

32. CBSE. Life Skills Education and CCE Hand Book. New Delhi. Retrieved from www.cbse.nic.in/cce/life_skills_cce.pdf
33. Hamburg, B.A. (1990). Life-skill Training Preventive Interventions for Young Adolescents. Washington, D.C.: Camegie Council on Adolescent Development.
34. Adolescents. Washington, D.C.: Camegie Council on Adolescent Development.
35. Vranda, M.N. and Chandrassekar, R. M. (2011). Life Skills Education for Young Adolescents □ Indian Experience. Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology, 37, 9-15.
36. Adolescents □ Indian Experience. Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology, 37, 9-15.
37. World Health Organization. (1996). Life Skills Education: Planning for Research. Geneva: WHO.72p.
38. Geneva: WHO.72p.
39. http://mhrd.gov.in/adolescence_programme
40. <http://unicef.in/PressReleases/333/Adolescence-Education-Programme>
41. <http://unicef.in/PressReleases/333/Adolescence-Education-Programme>
42. [www.unicef.org/lebanon/programs_8008.htm](http://unicef.in/PressReleases/333/Adolescence-Education-Programme)

Conclusion

Leadership is a necessary quality required for students today. In a competitive world, standing out in the crowd is very important. Every student has what it takes to be a leader. Leadership skill enhances the time management skills of the students. Students can plan their schedule accordingly. Students are able to achieve their goals in a better way through leadership skills. Students who possess leadership skills are aware of their rights and duties. They know how to get things done. Those possessing leadership skills are team players. They know how to lead others. Leadership skill makes students more confident and they never hesitate in accepting challenges of life. Leadership skills help students to enhance their social skills. Students also learn how to communicate effectively. Leadership skills help students to make better connections with others. Students possessing leadership skills are society-people. They have the ability to lead and find the solutions for problems like pollution, corruption, unemployment and social conflicts.

References:

1. Aparna.N and Raakhee A.S (2011). Life Skill Education for Adolescents: its Relevance and Importance. GESJ: Education Science and Psychology, 2 (9), 3-7.
2. Bharath, S., Kumar, K.V. (2008). Health Promotion using Life Skills Education Approach for Adolescents in Schools □ Development of a Model. Journal of Indian Association of Child & Adolescent Mental Health, 4(1),5 □11.
3. CBSE. Life Skills Education and CCE Hand Book. New Delhi. Retrieved from www.cbse.nic.in/cce/life_skills_cce.pdf
4. Hamburg, B.A. (1990). Life-skill Training Preventive Interventions for Young Adolescents. Washington, D.C.: Camegie Council on Adolescent Development.
5. Vranda, M.N. and Chandrassekar, R. M. (2011). Life Skills Education for Young Adolescents □ Indian Experience. Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology, 37, 9-15.
6. World Health Organization. (1996). Life Skills Education: Planning for Research. Geneva: WHO.72p.
7. http://mhrd.gov.in/adolescence_programme
8. <http://unicef.in/PressReleases/333/Adolescence-Education-Programme>
9. www.unicef.org/lebanon/programs_8008.htm
10. Aparna, and Raakhee, A.S., (2011). Life Skill Education for Adolescents: Its Relevance and Importance, GESJ: Education Science and Psychology No.2(19) ISSN 1512-1801
11. Chhadva, D., and Kacker, P. (2013). Effectiveness of life Skill Education on Adolescents. International Journal of Research in Education Methodology, 3(1), 213.
12. Dhingra, R. and Chauhan., K. S. (2017). Assessment of life skills of adolescents in relation to selected variables. International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, 7(8), 1-12.
13. Iqbal, N. (2009). Impact of Life Skill Training on Self-esteem, Adjustment and Empathy among Adolescents. Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology, (35), 61-70
14. Monteiro R., and Shetty L., (2016) "Introduction of Life Skills Education in curriculum for creative and positive social functioning among young students" International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME) ISSN (Online): 2455 - 4200
15. (www.rdmodernresearch.com) Volume I, Issue I, 2016
16. UNICEF, (2005). Life Skills-Based Education in South Asia, Nepal: UNICEF, Regional Office, Kathmandu.
17. UNICEF (2012). Global Evaluation of Life Skills Education Programs. New York: United Nations Children's Fund,
18. Vranda, M., and Rao, M. (2011). Life Skills Education for Young Adolescents and Indian Experience. Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology, 37(Special Issue), 9-15.
19. World Health Organisation (WHO) (1993). Life Skills Education for Children and Adolescents in School: Programme on Mental Health.
20. Yadav P., and Iqbal N, (2009). Impact of Life Skill Training on Self-esteem, Adjustment and Empathy among Adolescents. Journal of the

Indian Academy of Applied Psychology, (35)
Special Issue, 61-70.